

Mixed valence paramagnetic trinuclear complexes of ruthenium and rhodium with *N*-alkylphenothiazines

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Eight new mixed valence paramagnetic trinuclear complexes of ruthenium and rhodium with general formula $M_3L_2Cl_8$ ($M = Ru$ or Rh and $L = N$ -alkylphenothiazine) have been synthesized.

N-Alkylphenothiazines possess anticholinergic, antihistamine and antiameobic activities¹. In continuation to our work², we now report the synthesis and characterization of eight new mixed valence paramagnetic trinuclear complexes of ruthenium and rhodium with *N*-alkylphenothiazines (NAP). The structure and trivial names of NAP are given below :

	R ₁	R ₂	X
Methoxypromazine maleate (MPM)	(CH ₂) ₃ N(CH ₃) ₂	OCH ₃	C ₄ H ₄ O ₄
Trifluoperazine hydrochloride (TFPH)	(CH ₂) ₃ NC ₄ H ₈ N-CH ₃	CF ₃	HCl
Prochlorperazine dimaleate (PCPD)	(CH ₂) ₃ NCH ₄ H ₈ N-CH ₃	Cl	2 C ₄ H ₄ O ₄
Butaperazine dimaleate (BPD)	(CH ₂) ₃ NC ₄ H ₈ N-CH ₃	CO(CH ₂) ₂ CH ₃	2 C ₄ H ₄ O ₄

Results and Discussion

The interaction of ruthenium(III) chloride trihydrate or rhodium(III) chloride trihydrate with *N*-alkylphenothiazines in the form of maleate or hydrochloride in ethanol medium yields mixed valence paramagnetic trinuclear phenothiazine complexes. The maleate and chloride ions of the ligands go into solution during the reaction and do not take part in coordination with the metal ions.

The analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) suggest a general formula $M_3L_2Cl_8$ (where, $M = Ru$ or Rh ; $L =$ methoxypromazine, trifluoperazine, prochlorperazine or butaperazine). The complexes are coloured, non-hygroscopic and stable at room temperature. They are slightly soluble in acetonitrile and methanol, freely soluble in DMF and DMSO and insoluble in water and other common organic solvents. They do not possess sharp m.ps. The insolubility of the complexes in water and common organic solvents and lack of sharp m.ps. support the polymeric nature of the complexes. The molar conductance values are 16–18 for Ru-NAP complexes and 26–28 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for Rh-NAP complexes, indicating their non-electrolytic nature. The thermal data show that all the complexes of Ru

and Rh decompose around 200° and at 190–240°, and attain constant weight at 450° and 500–580°, respectively. The final mass-loss suffered by the complexes is in good agreement with the calculated value in each case. The magnetic moment values of the complexes are 1.92–2.20 B.M. for Ru-NAP complexes and 1.20–1.44 B.M. for Rh-NAP complexes which are low per trimer. The paramagnetism of the complexes indicates the presence of $M(II)$ in the complexes which suggests that the structure is non-rigid with good scope for superexchange. It is also possible that the metal atoms may not be purely either $M(II)$ or $M(III)$, but carry fractional charges. *N*-Alkylphenothiazines being good reducing agents³ may bring about the reduction of $M(III)$ to $M(II)$.

Table 1. Physical data of Ru and Rh complexes*

Compd.	Colour	Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
Ru ₃ (MP) ₂ Cl ₈	Brown	18.0	1.92
Ru ₃ (TFP) ₂ Cl ₈	Brown	16.0	2.20
Ru ₃ (PCP) ₂ Cl ₈	Brown	16.2	2.18
Ru ₃ (BP) ₂ Cl ₈	Brown	16.1	2.16
Rh ₃ (MP) ₂ Cl ₈	Red	28.0	1.20
Rh ₃ (TFP) ₂ Cl ₈	Red	26.0	1.44
Rh ₃ (PCP) ₂ Cl ₈	Brown	27.5	1.40
Rh ₃ (BP) ₂ Cl ₈	Brown	26.8	1.42

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and Cl analyses.

EPR spectra : The EPR spectra of the complexes at LNT exhibit three anisotropic signals⁴ confirming the presence of $M(II)$. A trimeric structure is tentatively proposed for the complexes, where two six-coordinated $M(III)$ ions occupy the extreme positions while a four-coordinated $M(II)$ ion occupies the middle position. The three metal ions are connected by dichloro bridges. Most likely the four chlorine atoms surrounding the central metal atom are at a larger distance not to cause hyperfine splitting in most cases. The four chlorine atoms surrounding the $M(II)$

are probably responsible for the lower magnetic moments shown by the complexes. The g values for the complexes are in good agreement with theoretical values⁴ (Table 2).

Table 2. EPR spectra of Ru and Rh complexes at LNT

Compd.	g_x	g_y	g_z
Ru ₃ (MP) ₂ Cl ₈	1.62	2.012	2.525
Ru ₃ (TFP) ₂ Cl ₈	1.64	2.008	2.522
Ru ₃ (PCP) ₂ Cl ₈	1.60	2.010	2.520
Ru ₃ (BP) ₂ Cl ₈	1.66	2.006	2.524
Rh ₃ (MP) ₂ Cl ₈	2.102	2.018	1.958
Rh ₃ (TFP) ₂ Cl ₈	2.102	2.010	1.966
Rh ₃ (PCP) ₂ Cl ₈	2.106	2.008	1.962
Rh ₃ (BP) ₂ Cl ₈	2.104	2.012	1.960

UV-vis spectra : UV spectra of *N*-alkylphenothiazines in methanol display an intense sharp band at 240–265 nm assignable to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. Weak ligand bands at 300–315 nm shifted towards higher energy region in the spectra of both the ruthenium and rhodium complexes. These bands may be assigned to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions and the shift may be due to coordination. The bands around 525 nm for Ru-NAP complexes and at 400–415 nm for Rh-NAP complexes may be assigned to $^2T_{2g} \rightarrow ^2A_{2g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ transitions, respectively.

IR spectra : It was reported that the ions R_3N^+H combined with Cl^- ion present in the molecules of *N*-alkylphenothiazines giving a broad band in the 2500–2300 cm^{-1} region¹. A broad IR band at 2600–2350 cm^{-1} of the free ligands corresponds to the $(CH_2)_3N^+H(CH_3)_2$ in methoxy-promazine and $(CH_2)_3HN^+C_4H_8NCH_3$ in trifluoperazine, prochlorperazine and butaperazine combined with X^- anion ($X^- =$ chloride or maleate). In the spectra of the corresponding Ru and Rh complexes, these bands either disappeared or reduced to a small hump showing that the tertiary nitrogen atom of the side-chain is involved in coordination. The free ligand bands at 2860–2825 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the heterocyclic nitrogen atom attached to the alkyl group⁵. In the spectra of the corresponding complexes this band suffered a significant positive shift suggesting the participation of the heterocyclic nitrogen atom in coordination. Thus the *N*-alkylphenothiazines act as bidentate ligands.

The far-IR bands at 490–482 and 458–475 cm^{-1} are assignable to ν_{Ru-N} and ν_{Rh-N} modes, respectively⁶. In the Ru complexes, the strong bands around 350 cm^{-1} are assigned to the terminal ν_{Ru-Cl} modes while those around 250 cm^{-1} are assigned to bridging ν_{Ru-Cl} modes. In the case of the Rh complexes, the bands around 355 and 280 cm^{-1} are assigned to the terminal and bridging ν_{Rh-Cl} modes, respectively.

From the physicochemical data, a trimeric structure is tentatively proposed for both the ruthenium and rhodium complexes :

Experimental

Ruthenium(III) chloride trihydrate, rhodium(III) chloride trihydrate (both Arora Matthey Ltd.), methoxypromazine maleate, prochlorperazine dimaleate (both Rhone Poulenc), butaperazine dimaleate and trifluoperazine hydrochloride (both Bayers A.G.) were used. Ether (dried over sodium wire), distilled ethanol, DMF and DMSO (AnalaR) were used.

Preparation of complexes : An ethanolic solution of *N*-alkylphenothiazine (1.91 mmol) was added slowly to an ethanolic solution of ruthenium(III) chloride trihydrate (1.91 mmol) with stirring at room temperature. The complex formed was set aside for 1 h, then filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous $CaCl_2$. The complexes of rhodium were prepared similarly by adding ethanolic solutions of *N*-alkylphenothiazines (1.91 mmol) to ethanolic solution of rhodium(III) chloride trihydrate (1.89 mmol) with stirring at room temperature.

C, H and N were determined with a Carlo-Erba 1106 analyzer. The molar conductance of the complexes was measured in 10^{-3} M DMF solutions using an Elico CM-82T conductivity bridge. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu FT-IR 470 spectrophotometer, far-IR spectra (polythene) on a PE 983 FT spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (DMF) on a JASCO-UVIDEC-610 spectrophotometer. EPR spectra were recorded on X-band Varian E₄ spectrometer at liquid nitrogen temperature (LNT) (field set, 3200; scan range, 4000; modulation frequency, 100 Hz; microwave frequency, 9.132 GHz; gain, 1.25×10^2 g; M.A., 4×10^0 g). Magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature with a Gouy balance using $Hg[Co(SCN)_4]$ as calibrant. Thermal analysis was carried out on a RIGAKU-TAS-100 instrument with a linear heating rate of 10^0 min^{-1} in static air.

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